

A319 DATA

GDF

30/3/94

FLIGHT REPORT A319 30/03/94 Great Dun Fell

Time 1	E.M.	Time 2	E.M.	Event	Height	Heading	
00:38:13				TAKE OFF BOSCOMBE DOWN			
				Transit low level to Brize Norton			
10:54:50	(1)	10:55:46	(2)	PROFILE P1	50 ft -	1000'	245 1000/min
00:56:29	(3)	11:15:33	(4)	cont' P1	1000' -	FL200	330 1000/min
1:23:22	(5)	11:27:51	(6)	cont' P1	FL200 -	FL240	330 1000/min
11:28:30	(7)	11:33:33	(8)	RUN 1	FL240		050
1:35:09	(9)			Start Descent into Carlisle			
				Start of Low Level phase.			
1:51:14	(10)	11:57:51	(11)	PROFILE P2	50 ft -	1000'	250 500/min
11:58:20	(12)	12:08:16	(13)	cont' P2	1000' -	FL075	210/180 1000/min
				Profile out of Carlisle up the Eden Valley.			
				Start H pattern over Great Dun Fell.			
12:09:26	(14)	12:15:19	(24)	RUN 2	FL071/FL073		330 Cloud top+500'
12:17:34	(16)	12:25:06	(17)	RUN 3	4500'		165 Cloud top-500'
12:27:12	(18)	12:32:12	(19)	RUN 4	3500'		340 Mid Cloud Run
12:34:02	(20)	12:42:19	(21)	RUN 5	6500'		165 Cloud top+500'
12:46:07	(22)	12:49:23	(23)	RUN 6	6500'		020 Tops +1000'
							Cross GDF
12:52:49	(24)	13:02:23	(25)	RUN 7	4500'		220 In Cloud
13:05:37	(26)	13:10:06	(27)	RUN 8	3500'		035 In Cloud
13:12:11	(28)	13:19:55	(29)	RUN 9	6000'		220 Tops +500'
13:27:56	(30)	13:33:48	(31)	RUN 10	6500'		310 Tops +1000'
13:38:32	(33)	13:43:58	(35)	RUN 11	4000'		155 Cloud Base
13:47:55	(37)	13:52:28	(38)	RUN 12	6500'		315 Cloud Tops
14:00:56	(39)	14:11:24	(40)	PROFILE P3	FL075 -	50 ft	180 1000'min into Leeming.
14:11:24	(40)	14:30:51	(42)	Climb	50ft -	FL250	115 1000'min
14:30:51	(42)	14:56:51	(43)	PROFILE P4	FL250 -	50ft	160/255 1000'/min Sea State 3
14:56:51	(43)	15:22:57	(45)	PROFILE P5	50ft -	FL250	255/160 1000'min
15:25:21	(46)	15:31:39	(47)	RUN 13	FL250		245/225
16:08:27				LAND AT Boscombe Down			
				Shut down at			51'09.00'N 001'45.55'W

A319 30-MAR-94 10:54:00-15:32:00GMT

GPS TRACK -- run no

A319 30-MAR-94 Height time series

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. P4

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 14519
Mean 54.2351
Standard dev 0.798381
Max value 54.9947
Min value 51.7387

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 14519
Mean -1.97401
Standard dev 1.17447
Max value 1.41392
Min value -3.16278

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 14519
Mean 2773.30
Standard dev 1981.53
Max value 7597.72
Min value 102.911

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. P4

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 14519
Mean 1286.62
Standard dev 376.022
Max value 1529.89
Min value 10.8835

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 14519
Mean 738.885
Standard dev 163.498
Max value 1000.95
Min value 377.204

CABIN PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 579
No. of obs 14519
Mean 992.366
Standard dev 67.1218
Max value 1033.42
Min value 842.693

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. P4

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 14519
Mean 268.479
Standard dev 11.3684
Max value 285.507
Min value 238.348

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 14519
Mean 261.526
Standard dev 13.8743
Max value 280.726
Min value 227.824

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 14519
Mean 9.189755e-02
Standard dev 0.218826
Max value 1.04749
Min value -7.551493e-02

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. P4

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 14519
Mean 2.79964
Standard dev 2.04131
Max value 6.75445
Min value -3.654300e-02

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 14519
Mean 65.0766
Standard dev 106.284
Max value 372.048
Min value 9.999998e-03

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 14519
Mean 3.779420e-02
Standard dev 7.139350e-02
Max value 0.354935
Min value 4.293363e-07

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

10:54:50 11:55:20 12:55:50 13:56:20 14:56:51

TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. P4

FSSP MEAN AREAL RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 905
No. of obs 14519
Mean 3.26731
Standard dev 1.88409
Max value 13.8313
Min value 1.74999

FSSP MEAN AREAL RAD. (MICRON)

3.93x10⁰ 4.29x10⁰ 4.66x10⁰ 5.02x10⁰ 5.38x10⁰
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile P1

Times 10:54:50-11:27:51 GMT

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile P1

Times 10:54:50-11:27:51 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile P1

Times 10:54:50-11:27:51 GMT

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile P1

Times 10:54:50-11:27:51 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile P1

Times 10:54:50-11:27:51 GMT

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile P1

Times 10:54:50-11:27:51 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 905

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile P2

Times 11:51:14-12:08:16 GMT

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile P2

Times 11:51:14-12:08:16 GMT

Parameter no. 575

Parameter no. 576

Parameter no. 579

1 second averages

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile P2

Times 11:51:14-12:08:16 GMT

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile P2

Times 11:51:14-12:08:16 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile P2

Times 11:51:14-12:08:16 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile P2

Times 11:51:14-12:08:16 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

Parameter no. 905

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile P3

Times 14:00:56-14:11:24 GMT

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile P3

Times 14:00:56-14:11:24 GMT

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile P3

Times 14:00:56-14:11:24 GMT

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile P3

Times 14:00:56-14:11:24 GMT

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile P3

Times 14:00:56-14:11:24 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

Parameter no. 905

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile Climb Times 14:11:24-14:30:51 GMT

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile Climb

Times 14:11:24-14:30:51 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile Climb

Times 14:11:24-14:30:51 GMT

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile Climb

Times 14:11:24-14:30:51 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile Climb

Times 14:11:24-14:30:51 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile Climb

Times 14:11:24-14:30:51 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 905

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile P4

Times 14:30:51-14:56:51 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile P4

Times 14:30:51-14:56:51 GMT

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile P4

Times 14:30:51-14:56:51 GMT

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile P4

Times 14:30:51-14:56:51 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile P4

Times 14:30:51-14:56:51 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile P4

Times 14:30:51-14:56:51 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

Parameter no. 905

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile P5

Times 14:56:51-15:22:57 GMT

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile P5

Times 14:56:51-15:22:57 GMT

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile P5

Times 14:56:51-15:22:57 GMT

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile P5

Times 14:56:51-15:22:57 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile P5

Times 14:56:51-15:22:57 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94 Profile P5

Times 14:56:51-15:22:57 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R1

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 304
Mean 54.0775
Standard dev 0.104743
Max value 54.2569
Min value 53.8985

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 304
Mean -2.72857
Standard dev 0.145827
Max value -2.47978
Min value -2.98005

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 304
Mean 7270.78
Standard dev 5.49821
Max value 7290.52
Min value 7260.69

11:28:30 11:29:45 11:31:01 11:32:17 11:33:33
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R1

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 304
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 304
Mean 395.187
Standard dev 0.308144
Max value 395.753
Min value 394.082

CABIN PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 579
No. of obs 304
Mean 862.878
Standard dev 0.769478
Max value 865.680
Min value 861.891

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R1

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 304
Mean 240.456
Standard dev 0.142401
Max value 240.846
Min value 240.189

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 304
Mean 240.126
Standard dev 1.69070
Max value 242.644
Min value 234.593

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 304
Mean $-6.444710e-02$
Standard dev $1.322101e-03$
Max value $-6.251208e-02$
Min value $-6.750544e-02$

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R1

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 304
Mean 0.444379
Standard dev 0.176750
Max value 1.24519
Min value 0.233601

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 304
Mean 2.56023
Standard dev 1.91537
Max value 10.0479
Min value 9.99998e-03

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 304
Mean 5.031295e-03
Standard dev 3.932156e-03
Max value 2.297147e-02
Min value 1.705863e-04

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R1

FSSP MEAN AREAL RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 905
No. of obs 304
Mean 7.10781
Standard dev 0.580729
Max value 9.83125
Min value 5.16773

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R2

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 354
Mean 54.7274
Standard dev 0.102377
Max value 54.9034
Min value 54.5503

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 354
Mean -2.67499
Standard dev 7.720826e-02
Max value -2.54083
Min value -2.80763

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 354
Mean 2193.87
Standard dev 22.9007
Max value 2229.73
Min value 2123.22

12:09:26 12:10:54 12:12:22 12:13:50 12:15:19
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R2

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 354
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 354
Mean 776.002
Standard dev 2.21852
Max value 782.861
Min value 772.534

CABIN PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 579
No. of obs 354
Mean 1033.42
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 1033.42
Min value 1033.42

12:09:26 12:10:54 12:12:22 12:13:50 12:15:19
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R2

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 354
Mean 274.171
Standard dev 0.812121
Max value 275.722
Min value 272.911

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 354
Mean 263.317
Standard dev 2.22565
Max value 267.052
Min value 258.914

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 354
Mean $-1.919738e-02$
Standard dev $8.208396e-03$
Max value $1.203600e-02$
Min value $-4.673701e-02$

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R2

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 354
Mean 2.32668
Standard dev 0.399954
Max value 3.01150
Min value 1.60367

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 354
Mean $2.333960e-02$
Standard dev $1.653438e-02$
Max value 0.114749
Min value $9.999998e-03$

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 354
Mean $1.821586e-06$
Standard dev $3.640237e-06$
Max value $3.729202e-05$
Min value $4.293363e-07$

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R2

FSSP MEAN AREAL RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 905
No. of obs 354
Mean 2.14031
Standard dev 0.890852
Max value 7.75017
Min value 1.74999

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R3

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 453
Mean 54.7192
Standard dev 8.270141e-02
Max value 54.8626
Min value 54.5736

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 453
Mean -2.67271
Standard dev 8.230782e-02
Max value -2.53695
Min value -2.81422

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 453
Mean 1570.71
Standard dev 13.3473
Max value 1596.34
Min value 1545.32

12:17:34 12:19:27 12:21:20 12:23:13 12:25:06
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R3

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 453
Mean 1316.71
Standard dev 23.5375
Max value 1407.90
Min value 1269.28

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 453
Mean 838.247
Standard dev 1.37512
Max value 840.865
Min value 835.609

CABIN PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 579
No. of obs 453
Mean 1033.42
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 1033.42
Min value 1033.42

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R3

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 453
Mean 272.428
Standard dev 0.133730
Max value 273.803
Min value 272.178

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 453
Mean 273.985
Standard dev 0.304311
Max value 274.526
Min value 273.164

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 453
Mean 0.422931
Standard dev 0.174455
Max value 0.876828
Min value 1.224023e-02

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R3

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 453
Mean 4.98368
Standard dev 0.259122
Max value 5.57835
Min value 4.01936

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 453
Mean 206.049
Standard dev 72.2079
Max value 348.362
Min value 7.649907e-02

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 453
Mean 0.179667
Standard dev 7.511885e-02
Max value 0.335253
Min value 4.038195e-06

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R3

FSSP MEAN AREAL RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 905
No. of obs 453
Mean 5.54896
Standard dev 0.915338
Max value 6.93816
Min value 2.22199

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R4

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 301
Mean 54.7742
Standard dev 9.070780e-02
Max value 54.9283
Min value 54.6178

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 301
Mean -2.70757
Standard dev 5.010686e-02
Max value -2.62653
Min value -2.80263

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 301
Mean 1270.94
Standard dev 9.86131
Max value 1290.27
Min value 1243.82

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R4

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 301
Mean 1024.78
Standard dev 33.1068
Max value 1105.06
Min value 934.322

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 301
Mean 869.597
Standard dev 1.04692
Max value 872.480
Min value 867.547

CABIN PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 579
No. of obs 301
Mean 1033.42
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 1033.42
Min value 1033.42

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R4

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 301
Mean 5.32185
Standard dev 0.191888
Max value 5.69336
Min value 4.60225

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 301
Mean 260.371
Standard dev 59.0923
Max value 343.634
Min value 4.42930

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 301
Mean 0.150508
Standard dev 4.558701e-02
Max value 0.232298
Min value 1.708127e-03

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R4

FSSP MEAN AREAL RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 905
No. of obs 301
Mean 4.81004
Standard dev 0.360264
Max value 5.32545
Min value 3.58124

4.4832 x 10⁴ 4.4907 x 10⁴ 4.4982 x 10⁴ 4.5057 x 10⁴ 4.5132 x 10⁴
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R5

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 498
Mean 54.7391
Standard dev 9.314507e-02
Max value 54.8985
Min value 54.5767

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 498
Mean -2.65353
Standard dev 9.425466e-02
Max value -2.49852
Min value -2.82890

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 498
Mean 2187.12
Standard dev 15.2255
Max value 2218.96
Min value 2156.40

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

12:34:02 12:36:06 12:38:10 12:40:14 12:42:19
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R5

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 498
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 498
Mean 776.654
Standard dev 1.47453
Max value 779.633
Min value 773.573

CABIN PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 579
No. of obs 498
Mean 1033.42
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 1033.42
Min value 1033.42

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R5

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 498
Mean 274.085
Standard dev 0.806920
Max value 275.685
Min value 270.322

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 498
Mean 264.341
Standard dev 2.19614
Max value 270.569
Min value 258.425

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 498
Mean $-2.322680e-02$
Standard dev $8.371628e-03$
Max value $1.434429e-02$
Min value $-4.941444e-02$

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R5

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 498
Mean 2.19927
Standard dev 0.353060
Max value 3.59093
Min value 1.35927

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 498
Mean 4.930861e-02
Standard dev 0.510727
Max value 10.7156
Min value 9.999998e-03

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 498
Mean 8.769158e-06
Standard dev 1.327975e-04
Max value 2.821178e-03
Min value 0.000000

12:34:02 12:36:06 12:38:10 12:40:14 12:42:19
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R5

FSSP MEAN AREAL RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 905
No. of obs 498
Mean 1.96693
Standard dev 0.620107
Max value 6.24953
Min value 0.000000

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R6

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 197
Mean 54.6970
Standard dev 6.377564e-02
Max value 54.8065
Min value 54.5861

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 197
Mean -2.60379
Standard dev 4.405519e-02
Max value -2.52443
Min value -2.67630

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 197
Mean 2190.09
Standard dev 12.3096
Max value 2210.31
Min value 2164.84

12:46:07 12:46:56 12:47:45 12:48:34 12:49:23
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R6

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 197
Mean 462.698
Standard dev 684.865
Max value 1529.89
Min value 0.000000

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 197
Mean 776.365
Standard dev 1.19221
Max value 778.813
Min value 774.408

CABIN PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 579
No. of obs 197
Mean 1033.42
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 1033.42
Min value 1033.42

12:46:07 12:46:56 12:47:45 12:48:34 12:49:23
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R6

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 197
Mean 273.682
Standard dev 0.651807
Max value 275.684
Min value 272.810

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 197
Mean 249.339
Standard dev 57.8713
Max value 267.389
Min value 0.000000

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 197
Mean -1.676604×10^{-2}
Standard dev 7.435173×10^{-3}
Max value 1.183142×10^{-2}
Min value -4.079296×10^{-2}

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R6

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 197
Mean 2.25160
Standard dev 0.470294
Max value 2.83836
Min value 1.42670

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 197
Mean $1.932889e-02$
Standard dev $1.316795e-02$
Max value $7.649907e-02$
Min value $9.999998e-03$

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 197
Mean $1.321289e-06$
Standard dev $2.243845e-06$
Max value $1.956397e-05$
Min value $4.293363e-07$

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R6

FSSP MEAN AREAL RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 905
No. of obs 197
Mean 1.99570
Standard dev 0.655796
Max value 6.24953
Min value 1.74999

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R7

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 575
Mean 54.7174
Standard dev 0.104107
Max value 54.8917
Min value 54.5320

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 575
Mean -2.65417
Standard dev 6.495211e-02
Max value -2.52163
Min value -2.73088

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 575
Mean 1574.22
Standard dev 12.0821
Max value 1598.79
Min value 1535.82

12:52:49 12:55:12 12:57:36 12:59:59 13:02:23
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R7

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 575
Mean 1171.97
Standard dev 137.026
Max value 1340.56
Min value 851.489

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 575
Mean 837.885
Standard dev 1.24510
Max value 841.847
Min value 835.357

CABIN PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 579
No. of obs 575
Mean 1033.42
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 1033.42
Min value 1033.42

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R7

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 575
Mean 272.180
Standard dev 0.246602
Max value 272.917
Min value 271.646

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 575
Mean 273.943
Standard dev 0.254936
Max value 274.457
Min value 273.212

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 575
Mean 0.514326
Standard dev 0.207469
Max value 0.949538
Min value -2.243461e-02

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R7

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 575
Mean 5.00947
Standard dev 0.365620
Max value 5.65101
Min value 4.03661

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 575
Mean 227.065
Standard dev 56.1035
Max value 332.012
Min value 7.650170e-02

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 575
Mean 0.174663
Standard dev 6.274962e-02
Max value 0.288953
Min value 8.680076e-06

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R7

FSSP MEAN AREAL RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 905
No. of obs 575
Mean 5.29879
Standard dev 0.504091
Max value 6.20210
Min value 2.94733

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R8

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 270
Mean 54.6664
Standard dev 8.062335e-02
Max value 54.8055
Min value 54.5260

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 270
Mean -2.61137
Standard dev 5.629189e-02
Max value -2.51218
Min value -2.70785

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 270
Mean 1273.74
Standard dev 11.3428
Max value 1302.53
Min value 1252.59

13:05:37 13:06:44 13:07:51 13:08:58 13:10:06
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R8

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 270
Mean 851.231
Standard dev 174.738
Max value 1054.56
Min value 473.511

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 270
Mean 869.301
Standard dev 1.20353
Max value 871.547
Min value 866.250

CABIN PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 579
No. of obs 270
Mean 1033.42
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 1033.42
Min value 1033.42

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R8

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 270
Mean 273.905
Standard dev 0.188622
Max value 274.604
Min value 273.553

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 270
Mean 274.618
Standard dev 0.397405
Max value 275.471
Min value 273.829

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 270
Mean 0.109390
Standard dev 0.107574
Max value 0.461672
Min value $-3.656615e-02$

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R8

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 270
Mean 4.66279
Standard dev 0.222768
Max value 5.19708
Min value 4.23496

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 270
Mean 150.886
Standard dev 118.098
Max value 340.716
Min value 9.999998e-03

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 270
Mean 3.633217e-02
Standard dev 3.253412e-02
Max value 0.122828
Min value 7.045106e-06

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R8

FSSP MEAN AREAL RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 905
No. of obs 270
Mean 3.37003
Standard dev 0.580109
Max value 4.65005
Min value 1.93499

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R9

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 465
Mean 54.6842
Standard dev 8.704240e-02
Max value 54.8331
Min value 54.5322

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 465
Mean -2.61810
Standard dev 3.731288e-02
Max value -2.56341
Min value -2.68696

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 465
Mean 2146.47
Standard dev 219.481
Max value 6422.43
Min value 2006.17

13:12:11 13:14:07 13:16:03 13:17:59 13:19:55
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R9

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 465
Mean 1507.28
Standard dev 57.1579
Max value 1529.89
Min value 1299.59

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 465
Mean 780.879
Standard dev 16.8417
Max value 794.340
Min value 475.331

CABIN PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 579
No. of obs 465
Mean 1033.42
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 1033.42
Min value 1033.42

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R9

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 465
Mean 273.941
Standard dev 1.35555
Max value 276.316
Min value 268.991

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 465
Mean 262.675
Standard dev 2.40170
Max value 267.669
Min value 256.470

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 465
Mean $-1.917697e-02$
Standard dev $7.500097e-03$
Max value $6.963477e-03$
Min value $-4.867586e-02$

13:12:11 13:14:07 13:16:03 13:17:59 13:19:55
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R9

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 465
Mean 2.12787
Standard dev 0.386387
Max value 3.10659
Min value 1.21456

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 465
Mean 1.581559e-02
Standard dev 1.001261e-02
Max value 5.737431e-02
Min value 9.999998e-03

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 465
Mean 1.176375e-06
Standard dev 2.175047e-06
Max value 1.956397e-05
Min value 0.000000

13:12:11 13:14:07 13:16:03 13:17:59 13:19:55
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R9

FSSP MEAN AREAL RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 905
No. of obs 465
Mean 2.00231
Standard dev 0.691550
Max value 6.24953
Min value 0.000000

4.7532 × 10⁴ 4.7654 × 10⁴ 4.7776 × 10⁴ 4.7898 × 10⁴ 4.7999 × 10⁴
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R10

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 353
Mean 54.7280
Standard dev 7.454783e-02
Max value 54.8453
Min value 54.5964

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 353
Mean -2.28720
Standard dev 0.122956
Max value -2.07905
Min value -2.50675

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 353
Mean 2165.50
Standard dev 14.7126
Max value 2197.31
Min value 2138.63

13:27:56 13:29:24 13:30:52 13:32:20 13:33:48
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R10

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 353
Mean 1079.05
Standard dev 649.145
Max value 1529.89
Min value 0.000000

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 353
Mean 778.750
Standard dev 1.42815
Max value 781.361
Min value 775.666

CABIN PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 579
No. of obs 353
Mean 1033.42
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 1033.42
Min value 1033.42

13:27:56 13:29:24 13:30:52 13:32:20 13:33:48
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R10

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 353
Mean 274.994
Standard dev 0.928986
Max value 276.159
Min value 269.336

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 353
Mean 255.493
Standard dev 6.14447
Max value 264.881
Min value 244.038

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 353
Mean $-2.386143e-02$
Standard dev $1.057937e-02$
Max value $1.457948e-02$
Min value $-4.985857e-02$

13:27:56 13:29:24 13:30:52 13:32:20 13:33:48
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R10

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 353
Mean 1.13246
Standard dev 0.560189
Max value 2.77187
Min value 0.473217

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 353
Mean $2.279055e-02$
Standard dev 0.102811
Max value 1.93593
Min value $9.999998e-03$

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 353
Mean $2.507838e-06$
Standard dev $1.980595e-05$
Max value $3.708720e-04$
Min value $4.293363e-07$

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R10

FSSP MEAN AREAL RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 905
No. of obs 353
Mean 2.10448
Standard dev 0.646486
Max value 4.58907
Min value 1.74999

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R11

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 327
Mean 54.6982
Standard dev 5.105083e-02
Max value 54.7843
Min value 54.6099

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 327
Mean -2.28507
Standard dev 8.584937e-02
Max value -2.13312
Min value -2.43526

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 327
Mean 1413.40
Standard dev 22.7914
Max value 1475.82
Min value 1373.78

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

13:38:32 13:39:53 13:41:15 13:42:36 13:43:58
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R11

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 327
Mean 801.218
Standard dev 123.228
Max value 979.948
Min value 521.357

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 327
Mean 854.584
Standard dev 2.38297
Max value 858.737
Min value 848.069

CABIN PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 579
No. of obs 327
Mean 1033.42
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 1033.42
Min value 1033.42

1 second averages

13:38:32 13:39:53 13:41:15 13:42:36 13:43:58
TIME (GMT)

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R11

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 327
Mean 273.164
Standard dev 0.194149
Max value 273.765
Min value 272.667

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 327
Mean 274.099
Standard dev 0.567103
Max value 274.943
Min value 272.508

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 327
Mean 0.170051
Standard dev 0.141945
Max value 0.481508
Min value -4.023860e-02

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R11

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 327
Mean 4.59046
Standard dev 0.297646
Max value 5.13235
Min value 3.94306

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 327
Mean 177.056
Standard dev 111.165
Max value 328.803
Min value 5.737826e-02

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 327
Mean 5.215161e-02
Standard dev 3.977289e-02
Max value 0.138746
Min value 1.288142e-06

13:38:32 13:39:53 13:41:15 13:42:36 13:43:58
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R11

FSSP MEAN AREAL RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 905
No. of obs 327
Mean 3.64803
Standard dev 0.617738
Max value 7.39089
Min value 1.74999

4.911e4 4.919e4 4.928e4 4.936e4 4.944e4
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R12

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 274
Mean 54.7219
Standard dev 6.298437e-02
Max value 54.8324
Min value 54.6139

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 274
Mean -2.27562
Standard dev 9.020772e-02
Max value -2.12122
Min value -2.42906

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 274
Mean 2184.16
Standard dev 11.9192
Max value 2213.34
Min value 2159.99

13:47:55 13:49:03 13:50:11 13:51:19 13:52:28

TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R12

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 274
Mean 1127.01
Standard dev 620.108
Max value 1529.89
Min value 0.000000

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 274
Mean 776.939
Standard dev 1.15485
Max value 779.284
Min value 774.116

CABIN PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 579
No. of obs 274
Mean 1033.42
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 1033.42
Min value 1033.42

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R12

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 274
Mean 274.894
Standard dev 0.461617
Max value 276.113
Min value 273.513

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 274
Mean 248.098
Standard dev 51.0187
Max value 270.184
Min value 0.000000

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 274
Mean $-1.371066e-02$
Standard dev $1.253953e-02$
Max value $2.904054e-02$
Min value $-5.013778e-02$

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R12

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 274
Mean 1.57354
Standard dev 0.465151
Max value 2.54112
Min value 0.698898

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 274
Mean 1.620591e-02
Standard dev 1.017441e-02
Max value 7.649907e-02
Min value 9.999998e-03

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 274
Mean 7.683035e-07
Standard dev 8.392458e-07
Max value 9.014460e-06
Min value 0.000000

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R12

FSSP MEAN AREAL RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 905
No. of obs 274
Mean 1.86592
Standard dev 0.419566
Max value 3.57940
Min value 0.000000

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R13

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 379
Mean 52.3085
Standard dev 6.328210e-02
Max value 52.4025
Min value 52.1910

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 379
Mean -0.163666
Standard dev 0.138060
Max value 8.751348e-02
Min value -0.393263

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 379
Mean 7606.24
Standard dev 13.5224
Max value 7631.00
Min value 7578.21

1 second averages

15:25:21 15:26:55 15:28:30 15:30:04 15:31:39
TIME (GMT)

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R13

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 379
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 379
Mean 376.745
Standard dev 0.729076
Max value 378.258
Min value 375.411

CABIN PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 579
No. of obs 379
Mean 843.782
Standard dev 1.09838
Max value 846.229
Min value 841.683

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R13

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 379
Mean 238.293
Standard dev 0.291951
Max value 239.466
Min value 237.922

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 379
Mean 229.339
Standard dev 2.10380
Max value 233.632
Min value 226.871

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 379
Mean $-6.565666e-02$
Standard dev $1.682008e-03$
Max value $-5.668357e-02$
Min value $-6.886545e-02$

15:25:21 15:26:55 15:28:30 15:30:04 15:31:39

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R13

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 379
Mean $-4.190990e-02$
Standard dev $4.852832e-02$
Max value $3.818303e-02$
Min value -0.135200

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 379
Mean $1.024074e-02$
Standard dev $1.464339e-03$
Max value $1.912477e-02$
Min value $9.999998e-03$

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 379
Mean $1.321068e-06$
Standard dev $1.133083e-06$
Max value $2.750047e-06$
Min value 0.000000

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

15:25:21 15:26:55 15:28:30 15:30:04 15:31:39
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A319 30-MAR-94

Run no. R13

FSSP MEAN AREAL RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 905
No. of obs 379
Mean 2.31854
Standard dev 0.748991
Max value 3.24985
Min value 0.000000

1 second averages